

PROBLEMS OF FORMING INTERCULTURAL COMMUNICATION SKILLS IN TEACHING A FOREIGN LANGUAGE

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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the problems of developing intercultural communication skills when teaching a foreign language at a university. The purpose of the article is to describe the essence of existing problems and suggest possible ways to solve them. The author notes that language education in modern society plays a leading role in the process of personal development and education, and the problem of developing intercultural communication skills occupies a dominant position in the discussion of the issue of teaching foreign languages at a university in the context of internationalization.

Keywords: *communicative competence, cultural peculiarities, multicultural society, linguodidactics, cross-cultural, intercultural communication, nonverbal, reflect, capacity*

Intercultural communication issues are currently a common topic of discussion when speaking a foreign language. It should be highlighted that efforts are being made to address these issues in order to raise the standard of young specialists' professional training in both practice and broad pedagogical theory. Foreign language instructors are undoubtedly interested in this topic because proficient language proficiency is the best means of facilitating cross-cultural communication. To fully immerse students in the culture of a foreign language, teachers currently working in this field must evaluate and modify their foreign language teaching methods.

Developing students' foreign language communicative competence in all of its diversity of components—linguistic, speech, social, compensatory, educational, and cognitive—is one of the primary objectives of teaching a foreign language at a university. We must not overlook the part that calls for multicultural communication abilities, though. We believe that before teaching students how to solve intercultural communication problems, it is essential to make sure they understand that intercultural communication is a rapidly growing field of study in many scientific domains (linguistics, cultural studies, linguodidactics, etc.). Its importance is growing daily in the current world since it guarantees a high degree of interaction between

people from various countries and cultures. It is impossible to fully engage in the life of a multicultural society without understanding and respecting the cultures of other people.

Indeed, the topic of how to live in harmony with other cultures and languages in the 21st century—an era marked by unchecked language and cultural fusion and mass migration—is now more important than ever. The complexity and national-cultural peculiarities of intercultural communication have drawn more attention as a result of this subject. A conversation of cultures, according to some scientists working in the field of intercultural communication, is what intercultural communication is all about. However, since culture is properly articulated through language, which stores all cultural values, we believe that there is no such thing as a clash of cultures.

It is well recognized that an individual's culture consists of his or her own worldview, way of life, mindset, etc. The following are the elements of culture that are most significant: 1) Rituals, conventions, and traditions; 2) routine conduct (proclivities, gestures, emotions, and facial expressions); 3) uniqueness in perception and thought; 4) artistic culture (movies, plays, paintings, music, etc.).

The secret to successful cross-cultural understanding is proximity. However, there is an alternative viewpoint. According to some scientists, communication breakdowns are frequently caused by cultures appearing to be close to one another.

There is one thing that will always be true: you can only take into account and comprehend the similarities and differences of multiple cultures by expanding your horizons and learning about other people's perspectives and worldviews. Many of the challenges that participants in intercultural communication experience become apparent during this cognitive process. First of all, linguistic disparities could be the root of these issues. Let's look at Russian and English for further clarity. Thus, for instance, there are terms in the English language that are consonant with Russian yet mean very different things. Occasionally, they are referred to as "the translator's false friends." As a result, a person who speaks Russian can understand a term differently from the other person and translate it according to his language.

As an illustration, consider the Russian translation of the English term "sympathetic," which is "sympathetic." This word could be interpreted by someone who speaks Russian as consonant with the Russian word "pretty," which could lead to misunderstandings in several situations. These words (data, list, accurate, etc.) are numerous. Interacting with phraseological units, which might vary greatly even among their constituent parts, results in the same outcome. For instance, "white crow" is the Russian translation of the English phraseological unit "the black sheep,"

which is precisely translated as "black sheep." And there are countless examples of these kinds of things [Labunskaya,1986].

However, a representation of a certain culture's language reflects not only that culture but also that culture's complete real environment (climate, living conditions, etc.). This is, in our opinion, the most notable example:

- There are words in Russian like "blizzard," "blizzard," "blizzard," etc.; in English, all you have to do is use the phrase "snowstorm," which is a common one.

This example best demonstrates how language may convey the standard of living for individuals. In this instance, the language reflects the national atmosphere of the nation in which it is employed. Second, disparities in social norms and value systems may contribute to communication challenges across cultural boundaries. Given that communication distance is highly valued by UK inhabitants, what a Russian may consider a "heart-to-heart conversation" may, in fact, be an invasion of personal space and life for a representative of British culture. Furthermore, the UK is known for its courteous citizens, who frequently employ the expressions "thank you" and "sorry." This kind of communication can seem excessively formal and courteous to someone from a different culture.

Nonverbal communication is a crucial component of intercultural communication in addition to the previously mentioned. Even though they may not seem like much, gestures may be quite important in communication and greatly influence how a discussion unfolds. For instance, if we do a comparison between Western and Eurasian nations, we can see that, in ours, smiling at a stranger may be viewed as odd and a breach of social norms. People in the West always have a smile on their faces. Even in situations where nothing good or encouraging is going on around them, they frequently smile, even to strangers. They are therefore viewed by some as being dishonest and deceitful. They are therefore viewed by some as being dishonest and deceitful. But it's important to keep in mind that for them, smiling is a normal part of life. Here are a few additional instances: While the British find the V-shaped finger sign unpleasant, most Europeans see it as a signal of success. A hand raised with the palm toward the speaker indicates to the other person to "shut up." [Grushevitskaya,2002]

All of the aforementioned challenges to effective cross-cultural communication can be categorized as a direct or immediate clash of cultures, meaning that the collision happens during genuine communication. On the other hand, cultural conflicts can also develop covertly, for example, through movies, novels, etc. This kind of crop contact is riskier because the barrier is less obvious. Therefore, we are presented, for instance, with the stark differences between the school lives of an American adolescent and the average schoolchild in Eurasia when we see Western

films about teenagers. Even the school setting has changed. American movies depict a separation between "tough athletes," "cheerleaders," and "crammers," among other so-called castes, which fuels the emergence of "bullying," or bullying that occurs in schools. In this sense, people subconsciously create perceptions about the historical underpinnings of the nation shown in the movie. This is the same reason why seeing one movie through the lens of one's own culture leads to conclusions about the culture of an entire nation, which is why indirect intercultural communication is risky. As previously stated, we are living in a time when civilizations are blending and intermingling. What was a few years ago the standard in the West but not so much here, has now seeped into our culture and gained widespread acceptance. For this reason, efforts to help future generations acquire intercultural competency must be focused in relation to the integration of cultures.

In our opinion, there are two main approaches to attain a high degree of intercultural competence:

1) *by strengthening one's capacity to reflect one's own culture, or restocking knowledge primarily about one's own people's culture; and*

2) *by delving deeper into the cultures of other nations. For instance, new academic fields that focus on examining the parallels and discrepancies across cultures could be introduced;*

3) *by encouraging critical thinking and introspection;*

4) *by encouraging tolerance and respect for various cultures, so that the student views cultural variety as an essential and normal aspect of life.*

How might foreign language courses foster the development of intercultural communication skills? The best opportunities for students' cognitive activity in the context of artificially manufactured interlingual conversation should be created in a modern foreign language class. The dialogues should resemble real-world scenarios as much as feasible, both conventional and unrestricted, that the students might come across in the future. The instructor is responsible for making sure that the speech scenarios employed in the lesson maintain the integrity of the students' mastery of language, speech, sociocultural, compensatory, and educational-cognitive abilities.

In conclusion, our students need to grasp that intercultural communication is a complicated and intricate process that involves more than just language proficiency. Understanding the norms, values, moral attitudes, ideas, mentality, and traditions of another people is essential for engaging in intercultural communication successfully. Studying the culture of those who speak a language as their first language is intrinsically tied to learning that language. There is little question that successful communication between representatives of different cultures can only be achieved via the combination of language and culture.

Since the modern world aspires to be transparent and understanding of one another, learning foreign languages is unquestionably important. We firmly believe that a field of study like "Foreign Language" has enormous potential to contribute to the internationalization of education and to assist students gain a better understanding of their own culture via exposure to cultures around the globe. Because of this, language instruction is crucial to the process of education and personal growth in contemporary society. When discussing the topic of teaching foreign languages in a university setting within the framework of internationalization, the challenge of fostering intercultural communication skills takes center stage.

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